

SWOT ANALYSIS OF THE ISLAMIC COOPERATION ORGANIZATION**Murodxonov Mukhammad Sodiq**

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Abstract. Organization of Islamic Cooperation - an intergovernmental international organization. It was founded at the 1st Conference of Heads of State and Government of Islamic Countries. It was established and adopted by the 3rd Conference of Foreign Ministers of the Islamic State. At present, the Organization of the Islamic Conference unites a total of 55 countries on the basis of religious commonality, including the newly independent Central Asian states, as well as the Palestine Liberation Organization. According to the OIC Charter, its purpose is to promote Islamic solidarity among its member states, strengthen economic, social, cultural, scientific and other cooperation, end racial discrimination and all forms of colonialism, establish measures for peace and security, and promote the rights of the Palestinian Arab people. and supporting his struggle to rebuild and liberate his lands.

Keywords: organization of Islamic Cooperation, swot analysis, country, international, economy, peace.

СВОТ-АНАЛИЗ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ИСЛАМСКОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА

Абстрактный. Организация исламского сотрудничества — межправительственная международная организация. Он был основан на 1-й конференции глав государств и правительств исламских стран. Он был установлен и принят 3-й Конференцией министров иностранных дел Исламского государства. В настоящее время Организация Исламская конференция объединяет в общей сложности 55 стран на основе религиозной общности, в том числе новые независимые государства Центральной Азии, а также Организацию освобождения Палестины. Согласно Уставу ОИК, ее целью является продвижение исламской солидарности между ее государствами-членами, укрепление экономического, социального, культурного, научного и иного сотрудничества, прекращение расовой дискриминации и всех форм колониализма, принятие мер по обеспечению мира и безопасности и поощрение прав палестинского арабского народа. и поддерживая его борьбу за восстановление и освобождение своих земель.

Ключевые слова: организация исламского сотрудничества, SWOT-анализ, страна, международная экономика, мир.

INTRODUCTION

The governing bodies of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation are the Conference of Heads of State and Government and the Conference of Ministers of Foreign Affairs and the Secretariat headed by the Secretary General. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation is headquartered in Jeddah. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation has the Islamic Development Bank and a Standing Committee on Cooperation in Science and Technology. Since 1975, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation has been granted observer status at the United Nations (UN). The Republic of Uzbekistan (since 1996) has been a full member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

He declared Tashkent the capital of Islamic culture. According to the decision of the 9th Conference of Ministers of Culture of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), Bukhara (Uzbekistan), Cairo (Egypt) and Bamako (Mali) have been approved as the capitals of Islamic culture in 2020. Uzbekistan joined the new OIC Charter on December 14, 2015. The Uzbek side recognizes the OIC as an authoritative and effective forum of the Islamic world, which recognizes our sacred religion as a factor of peace and development. Consequently, we are interested in the strengthening of this Organization and the consistent development of our relations. Official delegations of our country regularly take part in OIC summits and annual sessions of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers. Especially in recent years, Uzbekistan's cooperation with the OIC has intensified and reached a new level of relations. The 43rd session of the OIC Council of Foreign Ministers was held in Tashkent on October 18-19, 2016. In his opening speech, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev focused on the priorities of the chairmanship. OIC Council of Foreign Ministers of Uzbekistan. As the head of our state noted, the theme "Education and enlightenment - the path to peace and prosperity" is symbolic, as it is the main idea of the agenda of the 43rd session. This idea is in line with the famous hadith, "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave." It is no coincidence that the initiatives put forward by Uzbekistan in this regard are directly related to the development of science and education. The importance of promoting and protecting the rights of young people in building development "is a vivid expression of our views in this regard.

RESEARCH RESULTS

In addition, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev took part in the fifteenth summit of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) on November 28, 2021 in Ashgabat. The President touched upon the international and regional situation, the economic difficulties in the context of the ongoing pandemic, and put forward a number of specific proposals on the priorities of cooperation. We need to take full advantage of the huge trade and investment potential of our countries, which have a population of more than 500 million and a huge market. On the basis of the adopted conceptual program "Prospects of the OIC - 2025" it is expedient to further expand trade, economic and investment ties between our countries, and most importantly, to achieve practical results, - said the President of Uzbekistan.

The head of state spoke about the situation in neighboring Afghanistan. The country is facing a serious humanitarian crisis, Shavkat Mirziyoyev said. Without the help of the international community, including its close neighbors, the Afghan people alone will not be able to withstand these ordeals. The organization has taken the initiative to introduce an annual naming tradition for the development of a particular industry. The President proposed declaring 2022 the year of strengthening interdependence in the OIC. At the end of the summit, the Ashgabat Consensus was signed. The document contains important priorities for further development and strengthening of regional economic cooperation of member states.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, based on the above data, it can be said that this cooperation plays an important role in the development of Uzbekistan. It should be noted that the friendly relations between the two countries are strengthening on the basis of cooperation. There are also a number of agreements on this cooperation with Uzbekistan, which are expected to be

implemented in the future and achieve great results. And we believe that this cooperation will bring great opportunities to Uzbekistan in the future.

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